

CHESS POSSIBILITIES IN FORMING THE CREATIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the possibilities of chess in shaping the creativity of students in the primary grades of general secondary education.*

Keywords: *society, education, upbringing, chess, creativity, young generation, creativity, paradigm, technology, innovation, pedagogical process, development.*

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ШАХМАТ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ТВОРЧЕСТВА УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются возможности шахмат в формировании творчества учащихся начальных классов общего среднего образования.*

Ключевые слова: *общество, образование, воспитание, шахматы, творчество, молодое поколение, творчество, парадигма, технология, инновации, педагогический процесс, развитие.*

INTRODUCTION

The ongoing processes of globalization in the world link the qualitative changes in the socio-political sphere of all countries with the requirements of the XXI century. Today's society is in need of people with creative thinking skills in every field.

The introduction of innovative technologies in all spheres in our country, in particular, the development of production on the basis of digital technologies, puts on the agenda the education of spiritually mature, creative, responsible young people in the education system. In recent years, in order to comprehensively develop the young generation (Z-generation) that meets modern requirements in our country, the government has adopted and implemented a number of normative and legal acts to further improve the education system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No. PR-4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system" pays special attention to raising the education of the younger generation to a new level of quality, creating the necessary conditions for providing them with modern knowledge.

From the above, it can be said that "it is time for us to change what we think and how we teach in the education system". Because it is difficult for us to say exactly what other qualitative changes await the younger generation in society in the future. In this regard, the creation of the necessary conditions for the full realization of the inner potential of the younger generation in the education system, ie the introduction of new methods and tools to improve the quality of education in the field and the development of unique abilities and talents of the younger generation. we can find solutions to problems. Only then can we think about a new qualitative stage of education.

Today, not only the young generation with knowledge, but also the creative, creative, enterprising and well-rounded person, who is distinguished by his talent on the basis of his acquired knowledge, has found its confirmation in the question of how, in what conditions, in

what pedagogical processes. One of the most important tasks is to develop recommendations for further improvement of the educational process based on the results of research that ensure the socialization of education.

In this regard, as noted by the President, Abdullah Avloni's words "Education is for us a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster" have become a criterion for the future of our country. If we change education, education will change man. Therefore, it is appropriate to quote his words: "We need to improve continuing education, to educate young people as well-rounded people".[1]

Indeed, human life is development, and development is the result, and the achievement of the result is measured by the quality and effectiveness of education provided to the younger generation. It should be noted that today, when the world's fourth industrial revolution has begun, it is important to train creatively talented young people by ensuring the subjectivity of the student in improving the content and form of the educational process in educational institutions in creating the pedagogical foundations of a new educational paradigm.

RESULTS

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that the development of creative abilities of the younger generation in the educational process depends in many respects on the effective interaction of teacher and student factor and their intellectual potential, the level of development of creativity. The content of the research work of a number of scientists aimed at shaping the creativity of students in the educational process also confirms our views.

In particular, in the research work of CIS scientists N.V. Bibikova, S.I. Gin, Uzbek scientist G.N. Ibragimova, "an important condition for the development of creative abilities in students through interactive teaching methods and technologies is the joint solution of learning objectives by teachers and students in the educational process". At the same time, special attention is paid to ensuring the subjectivity of students in the educational process, the effective use of modern methods of pedagogical technologies such as "Brainstorming", "Buratina in the country of mathematicians", "Problem search". In this regard, we quote the following views of V.N. Drujinin: "From a pedagogical point of view, the development of creativity has an important age. Especially in children aged 6-7, creativity begins to develop under the influence of favorable environmental factors"[4].

Thus, the organization of the educational process in the primary grades on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies with the effective use of modern methods of teaching has a positive effect on the formation of students' creativity. In her final conclusions, N.V. Bibikova also confirms our opinion that "it is logical to assume that the targeted pedagogical process has a significant positive impact on the nature of the dynamics of creative development of young students".

Also, some aspects of the model of developing the creativity of young schoolchildren in the pedagogical process are reflected in J. Renzulli's "Model of development in school education". The content of this model is as follows:

- the main tasks of the first type of development are: to identify and develop students' interests, then lead to independent research, and determine the choice of the second type of development.

- the second type of development focuses on shaping students' skills and competencies at the level of their abilities, without which the realization of skills is not possible. The second type

of development includes: lessons focused on the development of cognitive and emotional processes.

- the third type of development is designed for the specific cognitive needs of learners who are intelligent, aspire to work independently, study the problem in depth. Here, as a goal researcher, the student feels, thinks, and acts like a professional[5].

Thus, it is clear from this model of J. Ranzullini that the model of developing students' creativity requires the improvement of the pedagogical process.

DISCUSSION

In summary, the level of formation of students' creative abilities in the pedagogical process in modern pedagogy can be understood as a developing interaction aimed at solving the educational and pedagogical tasks of the subjects of the educational process.

A number of scholars link the formation of creativity in the learning process with a number of qualities of learners. For example, Dj.Gilford emphasizes creativity as memory, E.P.Torrens called creativity as the human sensory organs, G.N. Ibragimova emphasizes that creativity is related to a student's sensitivity, intuition, imagination, research, and reflection.

Here we quote the words of Abu Nasr al-Farabi: "The human body, brain, and senses exist from birth, but mental knowledge, spirituality, spirituality, and moral character come into being in communication with other people". Man possesses them during his activity, achieves them[3].

This means that the character of keratinism is born in every person, and it is formed and developed under the influence of the human sensory organs, future activity, the environment.

One of the tools that will have a positive impact on the implementation of the paradigm of developing knowledge, skills and abilities of the younger generation in the educational process in general secondary and secondary special education institutions is the inclusion of Chess in the school curriculum.

In order to create the necessary conditions for the intellectual and cultural development of the younger generation through the introduction of chess in the educational process in our country the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PR-4954 of January 14, 2021 "On measures to further improve and popularize chess and improve the system of training chess players" was adopted and is being implemented.

On the basis of this decision, Chess training was organized on the basis of an 18-hour plan for 2nd, 3rd and 4th grade students of 1,000 general secondary and secondary special educational institutions of the Republic in the field of physical education. The analysis confirms that today in many countries around the world, special attention is paid to the introduction of chess in school education[2].

CONCLUSIONS

A number of scholars and experts say that the introduction of chess in the educational process will serve to improve the quality of education in schools. Chess is a game with a complex set of rules, and the individual level of the game depends on the player's expression of these rules, their creative use, and their ability to anticipate the outcome of the game. Teachers can use chess as a learning strategy to develop intellectual processes such as attention, memory, concentration, creativity, and reasoning (Krogus, 1972). Or it can be used to reinforce skills such as focusing, identifying and solving problems, planning strategies, creativity, and for students with poorly mastered thinking clearly (Storey, 2000)[6].

P. Govergen, a professor at the University of Sydney, in his book *The Importance of Chess as a Mechanism for the Development of Our Children's Brains*, emphasizes the educational value of chess, which also stimulates brain development. A group of psychologists led by psychologist Ruben Arzumutyan, a member of the Armenian Chess Federation, is studying the effects of chess on children's brains. R. Arzumutyan emphasizes that chess develops creative thinking and the ability to make comparative analysis and contributes to the formation of personality[7].

In conclusion, we can say that chess is one of the tools that shape the creativity of primary school students.

REFERENCES

1. Speech by Sh. Mirziyoyev at the conference dedicated to the 30th anniversary of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4954 of January 14, 2021 "On measures to further improve and popularize chess and improve the system of training chess players".
3. Abu Nasr Faroobi. *A city of noble people*. Yulduzcha, 2008. 224 pages.
4. V.N. Druzhinin. *Psychology of general abilities* / - St. Petersburg; publishing house "Peter" 2000.
5. Model of enrichment J. Renzulli. <https://infopedia.su/7x629b.html>
6. Fotinica Gliga a *, Petru Iulian Flesner b *Magazine Name: Procedia - Social Sciences and Behaviorism* 116 (2014) 962 – 967
7. <http://uniques.uz/Chess.html>
8. Jurayev, R. K., & Karakhanova, L. M. (2020). Scientific And Methodical Bases Of The Use Of Electronic Educational Resources In Teaching Biology In General Educational Schools. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(8), 3500-3505.
9. Karakhonova L. M. Using the electronic educational resources in biology lessons //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY. – 2019. – С. 35-39.
10. Karakhanova L. M. USE OF MEDIERE RESOURCES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF BIOLOGY IN SCHOOLS //International Scientific Review of the problems of pedagogy and psychology. – 2018. – С. 68-70.
11. Сафарова Р. Г. и др. Ўқувчи-ёшларни оммавий маданият хуружларидан химоя қилишнинг назарий-методологик асослари. – 2017.
12. Джураев Р. Х., Карахонова Л. М. Медиаобразование как фактор повышения качества обучения школьников //Образование через всю жизнь: непрерывное образование в интересах устойчивого развития. – 2013. – Т. 11. – №. 2. – С. 322-323.
13. Караханова Л. 6. DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE BASED ON THE USE OF 3D EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE BIOLOGY EDUCATION //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 55-59.
14. Kharaxonova L. M. SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF MEDIA EDUCATION AND ITS USE IN HIGH SCHOOLS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. CSPI conference 3. – С. 278-284.

15. Musokhonovna K. L. ICT-As a means of achieving new educational results in teaching natural disciplines in secondary schools //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 10. – С. 315-321.
16. ДЖУРАЕВ Р. Х., КАРАХАНОВА Л. М. Модель организации исследовательской деятельности учащихся 10 классов при преподавании физики и биологии //International journal of discourse on Innovation, integration and education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 295-299.
17. Dzhuraev R. K., Karakhanova L. M. Model of the organization of research activities of 10th grade students in teaching physics and biology //International journal of discourse on Innovation, integration and education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 01. – С. 296-300.
18. Мусахоновна Қ. Л. УЗЛУКСИЗ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА БИОЛОГИЯ ФАНИДАН САМАРАДОРЛИККА ЭРИШИШДА ЭЛЕКТРОН ТАЪЛИМИЙ ВОСИТАЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АСОСЛАРИ //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. В3. – С. 577-585.